

Wellcome Sanger Institute, Tree of Life programme author list

Tree of Life Faculty

Lead: Mark Blaxter

Associate Faculty: Richard Durbin, Mara Lawniczak, Eric Miska, Joana Meier

Associate Director: Delivery and Operations

Ed Symons

Head of Production Genomics

Kerstin Howe

Tree of Life Laboratory

Lead: Caroline Howard

Adam Bates, Isabelle Clayton-Lucey, Amy Denton, Andrew Griffiths, Benjamin Jackson, Haddijatou Mbye, Graeme Oatley, Juan Pablo Narváez Gomez, Liam Prestwood, David Rowland, Abitha Thomas, Aarushi Vaidya

Tree of Life Assembly

Lead: Shane A. McCarthy

Erik Aunin, William Eagles, Noah Gettle, Ksenia Krasheninnikova, Eugene Myers, Damon-Lee Pointon, Ying Sims, James Torrance, Marcela Uliano-Silva, Chenxi Zhou

Genome Reference Informatics Team

Lead: Jonathan Wood

Dominic Absolon, Joanna Collins, Michael Paulini, Sarah Pelan, Alan Tracey

Informatics Infrastructure

Lead: Matthieu Muffato

Paul Davis, Cibele Gomes de Sotero Caio, Guoying Qi, Cibin Sadasivan Baby, Priyanka Surana

Project Management and Operations

Lead: Manuel Batista

Theodora Anderson, Leah Bacon, Jess Bernard, Sinead Calnan, Molly Carter, Nikki Chapman, Stephanie Fagan, Nancy Holroyd, Chloe Leech, Luke Lythgoe, Victoria McKenna, Cam Muyo, Hayou Niu, Radka Platte, Ian Still

Enabling Platforms

Lead: Andrew Varley

Kiernan Harding, Charlie Hathaway, Ashish Mittal, Edward Mouldsdale

Blaxter Faculty group

Richard Challis, Pablo Gonzalez, Manuela Kieninger, Erna King, Sujai Kumar, Lewis Stevens, Jessica Thomas-Thorpe, Emmelien Vancaester, Claudia Weber, Charlotte Wright

Lawniczak Faculty group

Physilia Chua, Cameron Ferguson, Katie Page, Lyndall Pereira da Conceicao, ChengCheng Zhao

Meier Faculty group

Patricio Salazar, Eva van der Heijden, Jonah Walker

All authors: Tree of Life, Wellcome Sanger Institute, Hinxton, Cambridgeshire CB10 1SA, UK